

Weathering of Silicate Minerals : Influence of Chemical Agents on Them

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Three clay minerals belonging to illite, vermiculite and chlorite group were subjected to weathering treatments by 10% hydrochloric acid and Sodium tetraphenyl Boron salt treatments. X-ray diffraction patterns of the treated clays show changes in mineral structures. The treated clay lattice of illite is however not much affected by acid treatment except that the basal spacing shifts from 9.80Å to 9.77Å without change in intensity. Vermiculite on treatment with excess of 10% HCl results in collapse of mineral structure. A chloritic clay can stand weathering action of acid to a longer duration and shows no change in basal spacing. This difference in acid attack between illite, vermiculite and chlorite has been correlated to their compositional differences in lattice substitution and charge distribution in the lattice.

NaBPh₄ treatments of illite and K-vermiculite show interesting changes, NaBPh₄ treatment removed interlayer potassium from illite to a minor extent, 9.84Å basal spacing shifts to 10.03Å. The interlayer potassium content of K-vermiculite is easily removed within seven days causing an expansion of lattice from 10.11Å to 14.71Å.

PREVIOUS studies of Correns⁶, Scott and Reed¹⁰, Marshall and McDowell⁹, Conyers⁵ show that chemical weathering treatments result in diagenetic alteration and partial dissolution of micaceous clay minerals with the liberation of Fe, Al and Mg from octahedral and tetrahedral layers of clay lattice structures (Rich¹⁴, Grim⁷). Such dissolution study is useful in determining the limitation of chemical treatments in X-ray identification of complex silicate minerals, order of stability and their free energies of formation, (Rich¹⁴, Reesman¹³).

The purpose of this study is (a) to examine basal spacing alterations of three silicate minerals, viz., illite, vermiculite and chlorite when subjected to acid weathering treatments, (b) to correlate release of Al, Mg from octahedral layers with chemical composition of structural layers and charge deficiency in tetrahedral layers, (c) to measure the effect of salt treatments like NaBPh₄ on K-release from K-rich clays and the corresponding changes in X-ray structures.

An attempt has also been made to study the kinetics of acid dissolution reaction on potassium bearing clay minerals.

Experimental Methods

Clay samples selected for this study were illite clays isolated from Nimbahara (Rajasthan) shale, vermiculite clays from Mg rich vermiculite from Hazaribagh (Bihar), K-rich vermiculite from Ranchi and chlorite clays from Sundergarh chlorite schist (Orissa) (Adhikari^{12,23}). The structural formulae of

the samples (original and sesquioxides free) were determined from chemical analysis and are shown in Table 1 (Majumdar⁸). The sesquioxides of the samples were removed by dithionite method (Aguilera and Jackson⁴).

HCl treatment

(i) *Illite (Nimbahara)*: 100 mgm of clay (< 2 μ particle size) were treated separately in small pyrex conical flasks (100 ml.) with 50 ml. of 10% HCl and allowed to stand for 7 and 30 days. The solutions were centrifuged after the specified contact periods. The amounts of Al liberated were determined by EDTA titration after the usual separation of Fe and Ti (Vogel¹⁵). X-ray photographs of the acid-treated clay residue after thoroughly washing with water were taken with a Phillips 1010 X-ray Unit with Cu target and Ni filter (Adhikari *et al.*³).

(ii) *Vermiculite (Hazaribagh)*: To study the reaction kinetics of acid dissolution of vermiculite, 50 mg. of the vermiculite sample (powdered to -100 μ size) were treated separately with 100 ml of 10% HCl at 27° and 54° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., 1 hr. and 4 hr. The solutions were centrifuged after the specified contact periods. The amounts of Mg released were determined by EDTA titration after the usual separation of sesquioxide.

(iii) *Chlorite (Sundergarh)*: The experimental procedure of acid dissolution of chlorite is similar to that of vermiculite. The experiments were conducted at temperatures 26° and 60°.

TABLE 1. STRUCTURAL FORMULAE OF H-CLAYS DETERMINED FROM CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

Illite (Nimbahara) (Original)

Al substitution = 16.25%, charge deficiency = 5.25, charge density = 5.1×10^3 esu/m².

Illite (Nimbahara) (Oxide free)

Al substitution = 19.9%, charge deficiency = 6.32, charge density = 5.2×10^3 esu/m².

Vermiculite (Hazariabagh)

Al substitution = 33.75%, charge deficiency = 10.80.

Chlorite (Sundergarh) (Original)

Al substitution = 34.62%, charge deficiency = 11.02, charge density = 17.4×10^3 esu/m².

Chlorite (Sundergarh) (Oxide free)

Al substitution = 33.88%, charge deficiency = 10.84.

NaBPh₄ treatment

To determine the amount of extractable potassium from illite clay (Nimbahara) and K-rich vermiculite (Ranchi) clays these were treated with NaBPh₄ buffered with sodium citrate and EDTA at pH 7; the procedure adopted by Scott^{10,11} was used.

H-clay (< 2μ size) from these samples was mixed with adequate amounts of reagent (2N NaCl+0.2 N NaBPh₄+0.01 M EDTA at pH 7) with occasional stirrings. After 24 hr. contact period the mixture was treated with the acetone and centrifuged. The residue was again treated with same amount of reagent and the process repeated for 72 hr for illite and 7 days for K-rich vermiculite. K₂O contents in the extracts were determined by Flame Photometer. In each case the residues after chemical treatment were washed, air dried, powdered and subjected to X-ray analyses.

Results and Discussion

Illite (Nimbahara)

The molecular composition of the clay mineral isolated from Nimbahara shale is shown in Table 1. Table 2 shows that treatments of illitic clay with 10% HCl remove 21% of the total Al content (1.9 meq) in 7 days and 37% approx. in 30 days. It is apparent that the reaction slows down at the

later stage, possibly the concentration of Al as well as other ions Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Mg²⁺ in the solution would govern the rate and equilibrium of acid dissolution reaction. A major portion of Al dissolved is probably derived from that present as free sesquioxide in the original sample and contaminated with clay fraction. This has been substantiated from the study of the similarly treated oxide free clay. The oxide free clay showed 7% approximately of Al release. Table 3 shows that the basal spacing of the clay residue after acid treatment shifts from 9.84 Å to 9.77 Å with equal intensity indicating that the clay lattice is not affected by acid treatment and K-release (nonexchangeable cation) from the interlayer region is 7% approx. of total K content (0.14 meq) in clay after 30 days.

Table 3 shows the amounts of K-release on NaBPh₄ treatments of illitic clay. It appears from the table that the rate of extraction is slow; only 6% approx. of total K content is released in 72 hr. after successive NaBPh₄ treatments. The release of K from the clay structure depends on diffusion from the interior to wedge shaped surface of the clay. The basal spacing of the residue after salt weathering treatments shifts from 9.84 Å to 10.03 Å; such an increase in basal spacings suggest that mica remnants contain lower interlayer K contents than mica components of original clay sample (White¹⁶). The difference in acid and salt weathering may be related

acids, the reactions were conducted at 27° and 54°. With the rise in temperature the release of Mg from octahedral layers is complete within an hour at 54°. A plot of ln Mg content (obtained by subtracting the amount of Mg released from original Mg content) versus time gives a straight line indicating that the reaction kinetics obeys a first order reaction rate. Evaluation of activation energy using equation

$$E = \frac{RT_2T_1}{T_2 - T_1} \ln \frac{K_2}{K_1}$$

gives a value of $E = 1.12$ K cal./mole. The basal spacing of the clay relics after acid treatment collapses showing an all surface attack (planar as well as edge surface) by acid due to lower resistance to such treatment. The chemical analysis of the vermiculite sample after the dithionite treatment showed practically no difference from the original sample. Hence release experiment of Mg was not repeated with oxide free sample.

Table 3 shows the release of K from a K-rich vermiculite from Ranchi (Majumdar⁸). On NaBPh₄ weathering treatments the rate of extraction of K is faster than that of illite (Table 3). Practically all the K content of this sample is released after six consecutive treatments within a week's interval of time. The X-ray diffraction pattern (Table 4) shows an increase in basal spacing from 10.11 Å to 14.71 Å and a complete absence of 10.11 Å. On the basis of K removal, it may be said that K-rich vermiculite more susceptible to attack by NaBPh₄ than is illite. This suggests that NaBPh₄ treatment altered the interlayer basal structure of vermiculite in such a manner that there is a significant lowering of the layer charge of the original sample (Scott and Reed¹⁰). This can be considered due to (i) Proton incorporation in the structure of the mineral forming an OH with the oxygen in the silicate sheet, (ii) Oxidation of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺ which is present in octahedral position. Hence the mechanism of acid weathering is different from salt weathering with minerals as this.

Chlorite (Sundergarh)

Acid dissolution study (Table 2) of a chlorite (original) mineral shows that 37.8% of total Mg content (0.37 meq) of the sample is released in 2 days, 67.6% in 8 days and release of Mg is almost complete within 3 weeks at 26°. When this experiment was conducted at 60°, it was found that the rate of dissolution is enhanced. 46% approx. Mg is released in 4 hr. A plot of ln Mg content in the clay residue against time gives a straight line indicating a first order reaction character. The E value of the release of Mg from chlorite mineral is found to be 1.37 K cal./mole. which shows that chlorite is somewhat more resistant to acid weathering than vermiculite.

Diffraction patterns of chlorite (Table 4) after treatment with acid do not show any marked difference. The sesquioxide free samples of chlorite showed only slight differences in chemical composition (cf. Mg content) from the original one. Hence Mg release from oxide free samples was not studied. This difference in acid attack between illite, vermiculite and chlorite has been correlated with structural composition (Table 1), Al substitution for Si in tetrahedra layers, charge deficiency, unit cell charge density. A compositional difference is to be noticed in the octahedral layers of illite, vermiculite and chlorite (Table 1). The octahedral layers of chlorite is populated by Al³⁺, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Mg²⁺, it may be regarded as Fe—Mg chlorite since Al replacement in this layer is more by Fe²⁺ and Mg²⁺ than Fe³⁺. The replacement of Al in vermiculite is more by Fe³⁺ and Mg²⁺ than Fe²⁺. The bond strength in octahedral layer of vermiculite is weaker than in chlorite; replacement of Al in Si layer of vermiculite and chlorite is almost equal and the octahedral layer of illite is mainly populated by Al. Charge in unit cell layer is -1.0 in vermiculite, 0.48 in chlorite and -0.16 in illite (original). Such differences in their lattice structure seem to be responsible for differences in resistance towards weathering by acid.

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